

INVESTIGATION ON THE PROPERTIES OF BARIUM FERRITE/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Owing to the excellent physical, chemical properties and good processability, epoxy resin has been widely used in the adhesives, coatings, and aerospace. Recently, the materials miniaturization and light-weight demands the high performance for multifunctional epoxy resin.

With the rapid development of nano science and technology, nanocomposites have gradually occupied certain market share. Compared to the traditional materials, nanocomposite materials have unique physical and chemical properties. In this paper, barium ferrite nanoparticles were synthesized by citric acid sol-gel method. The polyaniline (PANI) was introduced via surface initiated polymerization method to improve the dispersion quality of nanoparticles within epoxy resin matrix. The X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), FT-IR analysis data showed that PANI was successfully encapsulated on the surface of barium ferrite with the weight percentage of 12%. Finally, the epoxy nanocomposites with different loadings of nanoparticles were prepared. The results showed that the tensile strength of epoxy nanocomposites was obviously increased as the nanoparticle loading of 10 wt%. Relative to the pure epoxy resin, the tensile strength of unmodified barium ferrite/epoxy nanocomposite was increased by 2.8%, and for modified barium ferrite/epoxy nanocomposite increased by 12.2%.

Based on the experiments and data analysis, it's found that the PANI was favorable to the barium ferrite nanoparticles dispersion within epoxy matrix and provided epoxy with the enhanced mechanical property. In addition, these epoxy nanocomposite exhibited the good magnetic, dielectric properties and improved thermal stability.

FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1: Stress-strain curves of cured (a) pure epoxy and epoxy nanocomposites filled with s-Barium ferrite (b) 5, (c) 10, (d) 15, and (e) 20 wt%

The representative stress-strain curves of cured pure epoxy and epoxy nanocomposites filled with s-BaFe₁₂O₁₉ and u-BaFe₁₂O₁₉ are shown in Figure 1. It turns out that all of these samples are of the

typical brittle failure characteristics, for which the samples are broken dramatically after debonding occurs.

Figure 2: TGA curves of u-Barium ferrite and s-Barium ferrite

Figure 2 shows the TGA curves of u-BaFe₁₂O₁₉, s-BaFe₁₂O₁₉ in the air condition from room temperature to 800 °C. There is no obvious weight change during the thermal decomposition process for u-BaFe₁₂O₁₉. In the TGA curve of s-BaFe₁₂O₁₉, the obvious weight loss from 300 to 500 °C arises from the large scale degradation of coated PANI polymer layer. It's estimated the BaFe₁₂O₁₉ loading in the s-BaFe₁₂O₁₉ from the weight residue of the TGA test is around 88%.

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